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Uncovering relationships between Miles and Snow strategic orientations, organizational and individual values, and creative performance

Abstract: The paper investigated structural relationships between the strategic orientation of business firms, organizational values, and individual values, and the effect of these on individuals' creative performance in an extended framework. In doing so, firms' age and size, i.e., years of business operation and number of employees, were considered as firm-specific contextual factors. The results provided support for the hypothesised mediation relationships, having implications for both theory and practice.

Key words: Strategic orientation, organizational values, individual values, creative performance

1. Introduction

Values occupy an important place as conceptions of desirable means and end-state of existence. Values are identified to operate at different levels, namely individual (like employees), institution (like business firms), and society or nation (Arieli et al., 2020). The literature also provides evidence for the predictive and explanatory potential of values; values in essence influence behaviours and actions of individuals (refer to Arieli et al., 2020 for an extensive review from the 1970s). This paper presents findings of a study that investigated structural relationships between strategic orientations of business firms, organizational values, and individual values, and effects of these on individuals' creative performance in an extended framework. We argue that, in the organizational context, values either organizational or individual underline the importance of people to achieve strategic objectives of organizations. This perspective allows to interpret, vertically, values as a tool to delineate organizational values and individual values from the strategy of organization. Horizontally, values can be used for different purposes such as employee selection, development, performance appraisal, and rewards within the organization. This approach treats values as the common language in an organization, which enables organizations to successfully operate, survive and grow in the business world.

The study presented is built on the arguments of configuration of values at levels of organization and individual (Rokeach, 1979) and the strategic orientations of business firms (Miles and Snow, 1978). These theoretical bases can still be identified as the most prominent and widely used in the management literature (refer to Arieli et al., 2020; Obel and Gurkov, 2022; Rabetino et al., 2021; Roccas et al., 2017). The study investigated 1) whether organizational values are predicted by the strategic orientation of firms, 2) whether individual values are predicted by organizational values, 3) whether employees' creative performance is predicted by individual values, and 4) the role of firm size and age in the strategic orientation of firms - creative performance relationship.

When considering the significance of the study, first, although there are some attempts to derive individual values from organizational strategies and values, this area is not yet fully developed. The literature reviewed in the next section such as Arieli et al. (2020), Desyllas et al. (2018), Hazzaa et al. (2021), Liang et al. (2021), and Park et al. (2020) provides ample evidence for us to propose that strategic orientations of firms affect organizational values, which in turn affect individual values, and ultimately employees' creative performance. However, previous empirical studies are rare on these structural relations in an extended framework. Therefore, our findings will essentially contribute to better apprehend contributions of values in the organizational context for the advancement of literature and making informed strategic decisions. Second, the literature argues that values do not necessarily result in organizational survival in its operational environment or enhance task productivity unless appropriate behaviours and actions are encouraged through organizational values (such as Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Meglino et al., 1989). The recent studies on values also provide evidence to suggest that organizational values that encourage external adaptation specify behaviours and actions expected from employees for organizational survival or enhanced task productivity (such as Hazzaa et al., 2021; Hoffman and Shipper, 2018; Liang et al., 2021; Park et al., 2020; Tesluk et al., 1997; Wu et al., 2022). As discussed in the next section, we investigated organizational values that are appropriate for external adaptation, which could influence employees' values and in turn their creative performance. Third, the study investigated creative performance, which characterizes novelty, appropriateness, and usefulness in performing job tasks at hand (Shalley et al., 2009). Today, creative performance is an inherent requirement from all employees but, usually, not prescribed in job descriptions (Abstein and Spieth, 2014). That is, the question of whether behaving creatively is a requirement for the performance of a particular job is getting less important today. Instead, potentially all employees, who were traditionally not required to be creative at work, irrespective of job roles and job levels across industries are expected to be

creative in identifying problems, scanning the environment and generating data, synthesizing ideas, and implementing solutions in the production of new and useful outcomes or responses for greater organizational effectiveness and survival (see Abstein and Spieth, 2014; Amabile, 2000; Chamakiotis et al., 2013; Dong et al., 2017; Shalley et al., 2009). The mechanism adopted in the study to identify and integrate the strategic orientation of firms, values, and employees' creative performance is novel, which both academics and practitioners would appreciate and willing to consider in future research and practice.

1.1. The study context

Most importantly, the study context is novel and addresses a constantly highlighted gap in the literature, i.e., the need for generalizability (refer to Liang et al., 2021; Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Park et al., 2020; Roccas et al., 2017). The study is based on a sample of 613 employees attached to 27 firms in information technology-enabled services (ITES) knowledge process outsourcing (KPO) in Sri Lanka, which is abbreviated as ITES-KPO. These knowledge process outsourcing services can be provided and as a result can be outsourced using the powers of information technology. Some ITES-KPO activities are market research, medical research, risk assessment and management, legal and intellectual property research, engineering and design, R&D, animation, and content development. On the one hand, a considerable number of ITES-KPO firms were established, during the last two decades, in countries where human resource and operating costs are considerably lower, like Sri Lanka (Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2009, 2010; Wickramasinghe and Ramanathan, 2022). On the other hand, employee turnover in this sector suggest that employees attached to these organizations do not depict loyalty to one particular organization implying challenges for people management (Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2010; Wickramasinghe and Ramanathan, 2022). Organizations must continue in search for personnel in terms of quantity and quality to achieve the strategic objectives of business. However, the attraction and retention of personnel is challenging due to the people-centric nature of ITES-KPO. Wickramasinghe and Kumara (2009) identified employees' capacity to perform creatively as one of the key capabilities sought by firms engaged in ITES-KPO. Organizations have options of hiring personnel with capacity to perform creatively, developing employees' level of creative performance, and creating an organizational environment that enhance employees' creative performance.

2. Literature review

2.1. Values

Values are “standards of conduct and conceptions of desirable means and ends of action, and these exist at both macro and micro levels” (Rokeach and Ball-Rokeach, 1989, p. 775). As a standard of conduct, a value signals what is good and bad or right and wrong, and uses words such as ought to, should, good, right, and fair to denote these in conversations. As desirable means and ends of action, the literature identifies two types of values, i.e., values that specify desirable end-state of existence (terminal values) and values that specify means for achieving goals of existence (instrumental values) (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Rokeach, 1979). Of these, instrumental values are more likely to describe values possessed by a person while terminal values are more likely to describe values inherent in an object or outcome (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Rokeach, 1979). Examples of terminal values in a social context are an exciting life, a world of beauty, a world at peace, equality, wisdom, and freedom whereas examples for instrumental values are honest, ambitious, logical, self-controlled, and imaginative (Rokeach and Ball-Rokeach, 1989). Further, Rokeach (1979) showed a functional relationship between these two value categories, where instrumental values describe behaviours or decisions required to achieve terminal values.

Over the years, theoretically and empirically grounded that values are small in number, deep-rooted, fundamental, pervasive, and stable or relatively permanent compared to opinions and attitudes, which are situation-bound in nature and more peripheral to the individual (see Arieli et al., 2020; Långstedt and Manninen, 2021; Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Roccas et al., 2017). However, Rokeach and Ball-Rokeach (1989) state that if values are completely stable, evolution would be impossible and provided empirical support for possibilities of changing values through interventions. In this regard, Luu (2021) provides evidence for the support human resource management practices provide in creating desirable individual values at work. Further, values can be organized into a value system, i.e., several values are integrated into an interrelated system. Such a system represents an enduring set of values that govern the appropriate standard of conduct and conception of desirable means and ends of action. Furthermore, values are multi-dimensional, where values can be fallen into different categories or factors (Arieli et al., 2020; Rokeach, 1979). For example, Rokeach (1979) showed that 18 instrumental values of the Rokeach Value Survey can be categorised into two, namely, moral and competence. In addition, values and value systems operate at different levels of specificity, namely, at the levels of the individual, institution, and society/nation (Arieli et al., 2020; Rokeach and Ball-Rokeach, 1989). The present study investigated organizational and individual values; the literature is reviewed on these at length in the next sections.

2.2. Organizational values

Organizational values, on the one hand, are the quintessence of environment an organization operates, its performance priorities, and commitment to its stakeholders (Allison and Kaye, 2015; Talwar, 2009). On the other hand, organizational values transmit the standard of conduct expected from its employees (Hoffman and Shipper, 2018; Talwar, 2009; Tesluk et al., 1997; Wu et al., 2022). In other words, organizational values are capable of governing employees' behaviour and decisions giving meaning to action (Rokeach, 1979). Employees are expected to hold organizational values as "ought to" or "should" in choosing behaviour and decisions when performing job tasks.

Organizations transmit a relatively small number of values (Rokeach, 1979), implying that a very specific or narrow set of values pertinent in organizations. Examples of organizational values are agility, corporate social responsibility, innovation, and integrity (Ciocirlan et al., 2020; Hoffman and Shipper, 2018; Jansson et al., 2017; Talwar, 2009; Wu et al., 2022). These denote end-states to strive for or outcomes valued by organizations from their existence. As a common practice, organizations incorporate these values into their philosophy, vision, and mission statements as well as organizational policies and procedures to convey a sense of identity, direct employees' attention, and guide their behaviours and decisions giving meaning to their actions (see Allison and Kaye, 2015; Liang et al., 2021; Park et al., 2020; Talwar, 2009; Tesluk et al., 1997).

Organizational excellence models like Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) and Deming Prize are being used all over the world to develop country-specific national quality awards, and all these promulgate as an obligation to adhere to certain core organizational values for the recognition of excellence. As a result, organizations are value-driven, and differences in values among organizations are lessening. Further, organizational values that are articulated into a value system should be shared among organizational stakeholders, including employees, for these to become a powerful force within an organization or to institutionalize (Allison and Kaye, 2015; Talwar, 2009. Tesluk et al., 1997).

2.2.1. Determinants and consequences of values

Indications as to desirable end-states to strive for by an organization could be determined by its strategic orientation while indications as to desirable means for achievement by employees could be determined by organizational values. Further, consequences of individual values could be manifested in all most all phenomena, like evaluations and moral judgments; the present study took into consideration *creative performance*. As such the key variables taken into consideration

in the study are strategic orientations, values, and creative performance. The literature relating to these three variables are reviewed in detail in the forthcoming sections/subsections. Further, as reviewed for H4, the literature provides theoretical and empirical foundation for contingency factors that may influence the way an organization is managed (such as Delery and Doty, 1996; Li and Rees, 2021). Considering the fact that a wide spectrum of external and internal contingencies could prevail at a particular point in a given context, and difficulties in taking into account all in a single study (refer to Boselie et al., 2005; Delery and Doty, 1996; Li and Rees, 2021), firm size and firm age were taken as contextual variables in the present study. Accordingly, Figure 1 shows the conceptual model; the main hypothesis is as follows.

Main Hypothesis: The firm-specific contextual factors of firm size and age are significant deciders of the strategic orientation; strategic orientation is significantly related to organizational values and in turn individual values, and ultimately employees' creative performance.

Figure 1

2.3. Strategic orientation of firms

Strategy is an explicit, deliberate, and conscious set of guidelines (plan) made in advance to determine the direction of a firm. A firm's strategies specify its purpose of existence, competitive domain, and resource requirements for survival and growth. The literature on strategic management emphasises the importance of understanding the level of strategy adhered to by a firm as a consistent pattern of response to its external operating environment (Allison and Kaye, 2015; O'Regan and Ghobadian, 2006). In other words, a firm's consistent pattern of response to "the operating environment can be categorised according to the strategic orientation of each firm" (O'Regan and Ghobadian, 2006, p. 605). According to Miles and Snow (1978), there are four distinct strategic orientations, namely, defender, prospector, analyzer, and reactor (for a detailed review see Blackmore and Nesbitt, 2012; Miles et al., 1978, p. 550-558; Kaibung'a, 2019; Snow and Hrebiniak, 1980b). We can conclude the arguments in the literature as Miles and Snow's strategic orientations can be used for the classification of firms within a particular industry; all four strategic orientations could perform equally well for a firm in any industry as long as strategies are well implemented; firms operating in a particular industry may pursue all four strategic orientations at a particular point of time; still, every firm has a particular dominant orientation of the four orientations based on its response to the operating environment;

this dominant orientation of a firm is identified as predominantly static in the short term and influences the firm's strategic decisions. The present study used Miles and Snow's strategy typology as the basis for understanding strategic orientations. When considering the present-day application of this typology, although different strategic typologies have been proposed in the strategic management literature (see Nandakumar, et al., 2011 for a review), Miles and Snow's strategy typology outperformed as the most prominent, widely researched, and widely used typology across disciplines over the years (see Aljuhmani et al., 2021; Anwar et al., 2021; Blackmore and Nesbitt, 2013; Desyllas et al., 2018; Herusetya and Suryadinata, 2022; Parnell et al., 2015; Rabetino et al., 2021).

2.3.1. Strategic orientation and organizational values

A firm's strategic plan establishes and/or reaffirms its shared understanding of the reason for its existence and aspirations for the future (Allison and Kaye, 2015). Its statements of mission, vision, and values are the most succinct reflections of this shared understanding. A value statement is an outline of a firm's guiding beliefs built on its consistent pattern of response to the external operating environment of the business or strategic orientation (Allison and Kaye, 2015; Amabile, 2000; Tesluk et al., 1997). Organizational values that characterize a firm are "reflected in organizational systems and procedures, organizational structure and design of work, and the physical design of the work environment" (Tesluk et al., 1997, p. 32). Kopelman et al. (1990) state that organizational values related to task support create an environment encouraging creative performance. According to Kopelman et al. (1990) task support includes support provided for employees by the allocation of resources such as time, budget, equipment, materials, and services to enhance creative performance. Therefore, the literature supports considering organizational values as "the most distinctive property or defining characteristic of a social institution". In our study, social institution is business organizations and values guide decisions made across an organization, every day. For example, Jansson et al. (2017) showed that values of sustainability are driven by strategic orientations of firms. Therefore, is hypothesised:

H1: Strategic orientation types are significantly related to organizational values

2.3.2. Organizational values and individual values

Employees familiarise themselves with organizational values through socialization processes offered by organizations (Hoffman and Shipper, 2018; Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Tesluk et al., 1997; Wu et al., 2022). Once get accustomed to, organizational values guide external adaptation.

External adaptation operates in such a way that organizational values specify behaviour and decisions of individuals at work yielding clearer role expectations, which are necessary for organizational survival (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Meglino et al., 1989, p. 425). External adaptation can enhance performance of certain individual outcomes, which require decision making, judgment, and creativity (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998). According to Tesluk et al. (1997), organizational values “allow active risk-taking, permits the possibility of errors, shares new insights, and opens debate and dialog to develop creative ideas to increase their potential, and signal and encourage the types of behaviours and actions that lead to creativity” (p. 34). Therefore, these values can enhance organizational survival or higher task productivity as long as behaviours encouraged through organizational values are appropriate for organizational survival or task productivity (see also Hazzaa et al., 2021; Hoffman and Shipper, 2018; Liang et al., 2021; Tesluk et al., 1997; Wu et al., 2022). In the specific context of creative performance, the literature identifies organizational values of risk-taking, rapid decision-making, competitiveness, and experimentation derived from the strategic orientation of firm could drive creative performance in employees (Tesluk et al., 1997). Further, when differentiating between individual instrumental values and organizational terminal values, Rokeach (1979) states that the former describes values “possessed by a person” whereas the latter describes values “inherent in an object”. Therefore, organizational values should first influence on individual values to ultimately influence employees’ creative performance, which is required by the organization for its survival. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Organizational values are significantly related to individual values

2.3.4. Individual values and creative performance

Amabile (2000) states that any definition of creative performance should focus on the production of outcomes or responses. The literature describes creative performance at work as generating new and useful ideas about products, services, processes, and so forth at the level of individuals for organizations to adapt, grow and compete in the chosen business (Abstein and Spieth, 2014; Amabile, 2000; Kurt and Yahyagil, 2015; Oldham and Cummings, 1996; Shalley et al., 2009). Individuals’ creative performance may provide “either a significant recombination of existing materials or an introduction of completely new materials” (Oldham and Cummings, 1996, p. 608). Individuals with creative performance can identify problems, scan the environment and generate data, synthesize ideas appropriately, and implement the solution (Chamakiotis et al., 2013; Shalley et al., 2009). According to Wang and Netemeyer (2004, p. 806) “creative performance is exhibited in many aspects of task accomplishment such as in

generating and evaluating new solutions for old problems, seeing old problems from a different perspective, defining and solving a new problem, or detecting a neglected problem”. In a study conducted in the ITES-KPO sector in Sri Lanka, Wickramasinghe, and Kumara (2009) defined creative performance as the ability to be original or inventive and to apply lateral thinking. While appreciating the different ways of conceptualizing creative performance in these previous studies, employees’ creative performance is conceptualized for the present study using the conceptual definition of Oldham and Cummings (1996), i.e., employees’ level of creativity and originality in the production of outcomes or responses. We have also operationalised creative performance using the measurement scale of Oldham and Cummings (1996). This conceptualization and operationalization were also adopted by Shalley et al. (2009) and Kauppila et al. (2018) in their studies.

Considering the relationship between individual values and employees’ creative performance, individual values govern objects employees acquire or pursue, principles they cultivate, situations they live through, evaluations they make, and behaviours or actions they engage in (Arieli et al., 2020). In this regard, Schmidt and Posner (1982) wrote “Some of the most critical decisions [individuals] make involve personal values - how much emphasis to place on immediate interests of the customers or the long-term interests of the company, ... and what behaviour to reward or discourage” (p. 12). Hence, individual values govern choices employees made in their goal-directed behaviours or actions at work. The literature from different country contexts provide evidence for effects of individual values on creative performance (e.g., Dollinger et al., 2007; Kasof et al., 2007; Kurt and Yahyagil, 2015; Rice, 2006; Sousa and Coelho, 2011). The studies that used self-reported creative performance (such as Kurt and Yahyagil, 2015; Rice, 2006; Sousa and Coelho, 2011) as well as organization-rated employees’ creative performance (such as Dollinger et al., 2007; Kasof et al., 2007) shown to yield similar findings. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: Individual values are significantly related to creative performance of employees

2.3.5. Firm-specific contextual factors - organization size and age

Previous studies theorized and empirically shown that the context or circumstances within which an organization operates is vital in understanding its management practices (Delery and Doty, 1996; Li and Rees, 2021; Ogunyomi and Bruning, 2016). The contingent theory of Delery and Doty (1996) provides the theoretical underpinning for various contingencies that may affect the operation of any organization, such as firm age, firm size, or whether in export trade. Further, strategic choice theorists (such as Child, 1972) argue that a firm’s choices concerning products,

markets, and technologies could be conditioned by contextual factors. It is also shown that a wide spectrum of external and internal contingencies could prevail at a particular point in a given context, and accounting for all in a single study is difficult (refer to Boselie et al., 2005; Delery and Doty, 1996; Li and Rees, 2021). In the present study, organization size and age were considered as contextual factors.

When considering the specific context of organization size, Boeker (1989) and Li and Rees (2021) showed that when a firm grows by employee size, it becomes more structured and formalized, and therefore, it is an important determinant in achieving strategies and performance expectations. Ogunyomi and Bruning (2016, p. 615) state that the number of people employed at a particular point in time can determine the type of business strategies adopted by an organization. Concerning empirical support for the effect of organizational size on organization strategic orientation, Blackmore and Nesbitt (2012) and Smith et al. (1986) found the number of employees as an important contextual factor in deciding the strategic orientations of Miles and Snow strategy typology. However, Thomas and Ramaswamy (1996) did not find the number of employees as an important contextual factor in strategic orientations of Miles and Snow typology. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H4: Organization size is significantly related to the strategic orientation of firms

When considering the specific context of firm age in terms of years of business operation, McMahon (2001) and Smith et al. (1986) argue that firm age is an important contextual factor in the strategic management literature that captures an organization's life-cycle stage and its achievement of strategies. Boeker (1989) and Li and Rees (2021) showed that when a firm matures in age, it becomes more structured and formalized, and therefore, an organization's age in terms of years of business existence is an important determinant in achieving strategies and performance expectations. However, Blackmore and Nesbitt (2012) and Thomas and Ramaswamy (1996) did not find organization age in terms of years of business existence as an important contextual factor in strategic orientations of Miles and Snow typology. During our review of literature, we observed that, first, only a handful of studies had investigated the relationship between strategic orientation and organization age. Second, these studies do not make any resemblance to the present study. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H5: Organization age is significantly related to the strategic orientation of firms

3. Methodology

3.1. Respondents and sample of the study

The ITES-KPO firms that provide outsourcing services to foreign clients and operating in the Colombo district were taken as the study population; Colombo district is the commercial hub of Sri Lanka. The firm selection criterion adhered to was possessing five years or more experience in providing offshore ITES-KPO services. We identified 31 firms that fulfilled this criterion. When selecting the sample of employees from these firms, the criteria adhered to were possessing three years or more sector-specific work tenure and one year or more firm-specific work tenure at the time of data collection. The organization structures of these firms are, in general, flat with about two layers of management and a large number of technical specialists or professionals; most of these experts possess bachelor's degrees or equivalent education qualifications. It is stated that organizational values can also be influenced by employees' values (see Meglino and Ravlin, 1998; Schmidt and Posner, 1982). For example, Meglino and Ravlin (1998) state "it is important to recognize, however, that objects or outcomes do not possess innate value apart from the value attached to them by persons. Thus, the locus of both types of values is within the individual" (p. 353). The previous studies also suggest that the values of top managers have a major impact on organizational values (Schmidt and Posner, 1982). However, values of individuals in lower and middle-level job roles have minor effect on organizational values whereas organizational values have a major effect on their values (Schmidt and Posner, 1982). For the present study, we selected employees in technical or professional job roles who create value for firms.

For the study, 659 responses were received, of which 17 were removed as incomplete. Of the remaining responses, 260 respondents identified their firms' dominant orientation as prospectors, 353 as analyzers, 26 (from 3 firms) as defenders, and 3 (from a single firm) as reactors. Respondents from one particular firm identified one particular type of strategic orientation (i.e., within firm differences in responses have not been observed). This led us to conclude that the firms primarily identify themselves as belonging to either prospector or analyzer strategy categories. Having 613 in comparison to 29 defender or reactor strategy categories make issues in data analysis. Therefore, it was decided to remove responses that stated belonging to the categories of defender and reactors. This led us to have a final sample of 613 respondents confined to prospector (43%) and analyzer (57%) strategy categories. However, confining the sample to one or two selected categories is evident in previous research too such as Herusetya and Suryadinata (2022). The respondents came from organizations with average business existence of 11.48 years ($SD = 3.24$, min. = 5 years, max. = 15 years), and the average number of full-time employees of 532 ($SD = 63$, min. = 40, max. = 1023). The average age of respondents was 30 years ($SD = 1.69$); 54% were male; all had bachelor's degrees or equivalent

qualifications. Respondents had average ITES-KPO sector-specific work tenure of 4.98 years (SD = 1.67, min. = 3 years, max. = 12 years), and the average firm-specific work tenure of 3.09 years (SD = 1.10, min. = 1 year, max. = 7 years).

3.2. Measures

3.2.1. Strategic orientation

The strategic orientation was measured using Miles and Snow's (1978) strategy typology. Of the four mechanisms to operationalize strategic orientations of firms recommended by Snow and Hambrick (1980a, 1980b), we adopted the self-typing mechanism, i.e., employees classifying his/her organization's intended dominant strategic orientation. We followed the data collection procedure recommended by Snow and Hrebiniak (1980b, p. 336). This approach yielded a response on a nominal scale.

3.2.2. Organizational values

The intention was to identify organizational values that define employees' core thinking at work, which are appropriate to the ITES-KPO sector under study. Of the five alternate methods recommended by Rokeach (1979) to operationalize organizational values, we adopted the fifth method and collected data from employees (see also Meglino and Ravlin, 1998, p. 357). In finalizing the measurement scale, we followed six steps. First, in search of an existing established scale for organizational values, previous theoretical and empirical work were reviewed extensively. Although we found the studies of Talwar (2009), Jansson et al. (2017), and Ciocirlan et al. (2020) were useful, these do not provide measurement scales suitable for the purpose of the present study. Second, a preliminary investigation led us to identify organizational values prominent in the ITES-KPO sector in Sri Lanka. Third, we isolated values that are prominent in the literature and values that are identified as important by the ITES-KPO firms that appear to fit into our study. This three-step procedure led us to identify 12 items for the study. As the fourth step, a panel of academics and practitioners have assessed the items to ensure face and content validity. In the fifth step items were pre-tested to ensure content and face validity (refer to the section on questionnaire design, pre-test, and data collection for details). The sixth and the final step was ensuring item measures' internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and construct reliability. We ensured these during the data analysis, as described in the next section. This 12-item measure is given in Table 1. Respondents were instructed to specify, in his/her opinion, the extent to which each

value is used as an important guiding principle in his/her organization. The Likert response scale employed ranged from 1 to 5 (1 = not at all important to 5 = very important).

3.2.3. Individual values

Individual values were measured using the 18-item instrumental values of Rokeach (1979). Of the two approaches recommended by Rokeach (1979), we used the rating approach. Respondents were instructed to rate, in his/her opinion, the extent to which each value operates as an important guiding principle to him/her. The Likert response scale employed ranged from 1 to 5 (1 = not at all important to 5 = very important).

3.2.4. Creativity

Creativity was measured using the 3-item scale of Oldham and Cummings (1996), which operationalised employees' creative performance as their level of creativity and originality in the production of outcomes or responses. This measure has also been used by Shalley et al. (2009) and Kauppila et al. (2018) to measure creative performance. The Likert response scale employed ranged from 1 to 5 (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree).

3.2.5. Contextual variables

The total number of full-time employees and the years of business existence were collected in ratio scale. In the analysis, these are transformed to natural logarithmic values ($\log \ln$). In addition, respondents' age, gender, and industry-specific experience were also inquired in the questionnaire, and these were treated as controls in the analysis.

3.3. Questionnaire design, pre-test, and data collection

The survey questionnaire was in five parts, starting with strategic orientation in part 1 and ending with socio-demographics in part 5. The survey questionnaire was in the English language; the English language is one of the national languages of Sri Lanka. The questionnaire was distributed to the sample mentioned above after pre-testing; respondents responded to the questionnaire anonymously to reduce evaluation apprehension.

3.4. Data analysis methods

Common method variance was tested with Harman's single-factor test; the data fulfilled the criteria recommended by Podsakoff et al., (2003). For exploratory factor analysis, principal component analysis with Varimax rotation was performed. Tables 1 to 3 provide fit indices.

Considering the complexity of the model, composite mean scores of organizational values and individual values were computed for latent analysis (refer to Proust-Lima et al., 2017). The hypotheses H1 to H5 predicted direct relationships whereas the main hypotheses predicted the path relationship. We used a series of regression analysis to test direct relationships while structural equation modelling to test causal relationships. Normed chi-square statistic (χ^2/df), comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) were used to evaluate results of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The default model tested in the main hypothesis included both groups of strategic orientations. To test whether the default model is true for both groups, we performed a multi-group analysis. We created an equal loading model following multi-group analysis procedure (see Amos Development Corporation, non-dated; Arbuckle, 2013, p. 377-384; The University of Texas at Austin, non-dated) and performed nested model comparison to compare the default model with the equal loading model based on the values of chi-square statistic and its significance.

4. Results

Tables 1, 2, and 3 shows the results of factor analyses for organizational values, individual values and creative performance, respectively. As shown in Table 1, the three factors yielded were named as corporate sustenance, management virtues, and ethical concerns. The composite variable had an eigenvalue of 1.404, explained variation of 70%, Cronbach's alpha of 0.772, construct reliability of 0.825, and average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.702. As shown in Table 2, the factor analysis resulted in two factors as proposed by Rokeach (1979), namely moral (focus on morality and relations) and competence (focus on competence), and these were named accordingly. The composite variable had an eigenvalue of 1.615, explained variation of 64%, Cronbach's alpha of 0.743, construct reliability of .808, and AVE of 0.584. As shown in Table 3, the factor analysis yielded one factor for creative performance. Table 4 shows correlations and descriptive statistics. H1 to H5 were tested using regression analysis. As can be seen from Table 5, the results support all hypotheses.

Tables 1 to 5 about here

A series of CFA had been conducted and created six models as shown in Table 6 to evaluate the causal relationship proposed in the main hypothesis. The results suggest that Model 6 (the main hypothesis) is the only model that satisfies the model fit criteria of χ^2/df near 1, CFI and TLI

close to 1 but above 0.95, and RMSEA value around 0.05. Overall, of the six alternative models tested, the mediating relationship predicted in Model 6 yielded a better fit to the data compared to the other five alternative models. Figure 2 was created to depict estimates for the best-fitting model hypothesised in the main hypothesis.

Table 6

Figure 2

Finally, multi-group analysis was used to confirm whether Model 6 proposed in the main hypothesis is true for both groups. The results of nested model comparison suggested that both default and equal loading models were true (Chi-square = 1.967, $p = 0.893$), suggesting that non-existence of significant differences between the groups. Therefore, Model 6 proposed in the main hypothesis is true for firms with both types of strategic orientations- prospectors and analyzers.

5. Discussion of findings and implications

The findings showed the predictive and explanatory potential of organizational contextual factors, strategic orientation, organizational values, and individual values in the work context as proposed in Figure 1 and empirically validated in Figure 2. The strategic orientation of a firm decides most vital activities of business such as how and what priorities are made, how operations and processes are defined and structured, and how markets and customers are viewed and targeted. The results showed that the antecedent of organizational values, which indicate desirable end-states to strive for by organizations, is organizational strategies whereas the antecedents of individual values that should be possessed by employees are determined by organizational values. In other words, the present study empirically validated that macro-level strategic orientation of the firm shapes creative performance of employees at the micro-level of the organization, and in this process, organizational values and individual values make a significant contribution. Most importantly, the literature on strategic management emphasises the need of making strategic responses based on the external operating environment. The results showed that strategic orientation influences organizational value system leading to external adaptation, and in turn individual value system through which employees' creative performance is influenced for survival and competitiveness of the business. The results also supported

organizational values and individual values as mediators between strategic orientation and employees' creative performance. Although not in a similar context, Shalley et al. (2009) showed that employees exhibit higher levels of creative behaviour when both individual-related and work context-related dimensions are present. Decisions individuals make in the work context are not only affected by individual values of the decision-maker but also by values of other entities (like organizational values) to which the decision-maker feel obliged to respond. Overall, the findings imply the importance of investigating the strategic orientation of firms, organizational values, individual values, and employees' creative performance in an extended framework, involving organizational contextual factors. Since empirical research combining all these aspects in a single study is extremely rare, the findings of the present study have implications for both theory and practice.

Concerning contributions to existing literature, first, our review led to identify three streams of literature that specify relationships between strategic orientation, organizational values, individual values, and employees' creative performance. The first stream of literature supports the influence of strategic orientation on employees' creative performance. The second stream of literature supports the influence of organizational values on employees' creative performance. The third stream of literature supports the influence of individual values on employees' creative performance. Concerning the first stream of literature, the studies such as Amabile (2000) and Oldham and Cummings (1996) supported this line of reasoning. However, these studies did not suggest the mechanism by which organizational strategies influence individuals' creative performance. Concerning the second stream of literature, the studies such as Tesluk et al. (1997) supported this line of reasoning. However, these studies did not suggest the mechanism of organizational values influencing individuals' creative performance, i.e., through or bypassing individual values. Concerning the third stream of literature (such as Kurt and Yahyagil, 2015; Sousa and Coelho, 2011), our results for H3 also support this stream. Overall, the main hypothesis proposed and validated in the present study is novel and provides a more meaningful conceptualization of relationships between the strategic orientation of firms, organizational values, individual values, and employees' creative performance. This can be identified as the main contribution of the study.

Second, any of the strategic orientation types can be pursued at a particular point of time, and all orientation types can perform equally well in any industry as long as appropriate internal organizational structures and processes are chosen to align with the orientation (see Blackmore and Nesbitt, 2012; Miles and Snow, 1978). Snow and Hrebiniak (1980b) stated that firms that adhered to different orientation types develop different distinctive competences to support the

desired strategy in terms of how to reach their market. As described by Snow and Hrebiniak (1980b, p. 319), prospectors have strong emphasis on product and market effectiveness (product research and development, market research, and basic engineering (p. 319) with compared to manufacturing efficiency (sticking with the existing pattern of products/services). Analyzers, on the other hand, tend to emphasize both product and market effectiveness and manufacturing efficiency. The present study investigated firms that have a strong emphasis on product and market effectiveness as well as firms that have a strong emphasis on both product and market effectiveness and manufacturing efficiency. The findings of the present study showed that the proposed relationship is true irrespective of the strategic orientation type of firms. In other words, on the one hand, organizational values identified in the present study specify desirable end-goals to strive for by an organization as determined by its strategic orientation. On the other hand, individual values identified in the present study specify standards of conduct and desirable means for the achievement of end-goals specified by organizational values. The present study investigated employees' creative performance as one of the consequences of individual values (as shown by Dollinger et al., 2007; Kasof et al., 2007; Kurt and Yahyagil, 2015; Rice, 2006; Sousa and Coelho, 2011). The strategic management literature (such as Snow and Hrebiniak, 1980b) also argues that even though a particular firm does not possess strengths on par with its competitors, the firm could perform well in the chosen market as long as it possesses capabilities of its own. In this context, the findings imply that the organizational values and individual values identified in the present study can be referred to as core values, and as a result, the proposed causal relationship is true irrespective of the orientation type of firms. Therefore, the results of the study make a contribution to the literature on both strategic management and values.

Third, from an organizations' point of view, individual values are at the core of who its employees are. Employees' values influence how priorities are evaluated, decisions are made, appeals are responded to, and how energy and time are invested at work. Hence, the way individual values drive employees has important implications for how organizations operate and succeed. When understanding that organizational values shape individual values and in turn their behaviours and actions, in the context of the present study employees' creative performance, organizations could identify means to influence individual values. Organizational values investigated represent values required for external adaptation. It is possible to assume that organizational values identified in the study are shared and considered as behavioural repertoire not only among employees of a particular firm but also across a particular business sector for the survival in the business environment. Therefore, the findings of the study imply that a relatively

narrow set of values identified in the study are valid and appropriately measured. As a result, the findings can be generalised to the business sector in which the study is conducted, i.e., ITES-KPO. Still, as stated earlier, when business excellence models worldwide propagate a very specific similar set of organizational values, the organizational values identified in the current study have wider generalizability.

Concerning implications for practice, first, as discussed above, findings showed that values have predictive and explanatory potential, and business firms can use value systems, vertically, to delineate organizational values and individual values from the strategy of the organization. This is the causal relationship proposed and validated in the present study. Organizations identify fostering employees' creative performance as a necessity in responding to the competitive operating environment of a business. An understanding of factors associated with employees' creative performance has become vital for survival. The causal model of the present study identified values as an enabler of employees' creative performance, and a way of fostering employees' creative performance by influencing individual values. Firms can use value systems, horizontally, for different purposes in the management of people, such as socialization and employee development.

Second, the present study identified the importance of instrumental values in individuals. Firms can take steps to carefully select individuals based on their values and socialize them on organizational values that are vital for the achievement of strategic goals of the business. One of the important implications of the present study, in this regard, is that a firm should implement (use) core organizational values leading to external adaptation within the firm for the achievement of its strategic goals, and employees need to be espoused to these as guiding principles in work performance. In other words, organizational values should influence individual values on what employees "say" as well as how employees "actually behave" (see Meglino and Ravlin, 1998, p. 356).

Third, the study identified ethical considerations as an important organizational value domain. Values represent non-visual elements of corporate identity. The values in the ethical domain demonstrate a firm's commitment towards the environment and its stakeholders. These values represent the organization among various stakeholders as guiding choices and leading to actions that the organization supports; behaviours and actions of employees are governed by these values related to ethical domains. Further, ethical values may contribute firms to attract ethical business partners. This may become important when considering that our sample constituted of export-based outsourcing firms.

Finally, the findings have implications for employees. Employees have to be aware that organizational values encourage them to evaluate their values simultaneously with organizational requirements when at work. Therefore, employees need to understand and practice that the appropriate ways of behaving and making decisions by them or end-states to strive for by them are most preferably organization based as indicated by organizational values.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented findings of a study that investigated the causal relationship between organizational contextual factors, strategic orientation, organizational values, individual values, and employees' creative performance. The findings provided support for the proposed relationship having implications for both theory and practice as discussed in detail in the above section. It is possible to assume that a firm may move from one strategic orientation to another in the long run depending on the conditions of its operating environment. Still, we have shown that the causal relationship proposed does not vary by the type of strategic orientation. Further, although the operating environment of businesses constantly change and organizations have to adjust to such changes, organizational values and individual values are limited in number and identified to be stable compared to opinions and attitudes that are situation-bound and more peripheral to the individual. Therefore, the propositions made in this study and the relationships tested could be expected to remain stable. Therefore, an understanding of the key variables of the study and their inter-relations is beneficial for academics, researchers, citizens who aspire to obtain membership in organizations, employees, practitioners, policymakers, and business consultants. Having said that, since we validated relationships speculated in the literature on values and strategic management, we believe that the contribution of the present study to the literature is the most prominent. The design of the study, proposed causal model, selection of respondents, and techniques used for data analysis allowed us to meet our expectations from the study.

7. Limitations and future research

Concerning limitations of the study, first, the measures used in the study relied on self-reports as proposed by Snow and Hambrick (1980a) and by Rokeach (1979). However, in addition to self-reports, Snow and Hambrick (1980a) proposed three other alternative mechanisms to measure strategic orientation, and Rokeach (1979) and Rokeach and Ball-Rokeach (1989) proposed five other alternative mechanisms to measure values. Therefore, future research could consider these mechanisms. Second, we tested causal relationships using cross-sectional data. Still, this is a

common practice in management research. Third, the study was conducted in a single business sector. The main reason is that the literature on strategic management identifies the appropriateness of Miles and Snow's (1978) typology to classify firms in a particular business sector. If different sectors were included, comparisons could have been possible between business sectors.

Concerning areas for future research, first, the findings imply that the causal relationship tested in the study leads to enhance employees' creative performance. That is, in the long run, enhanced creative performance could lead to make better strategic level planning, in turn influencing organizational values, and ultimately further enhancing employees' creative performance. This type of endogeneity is possible in all most all organization contexts involving various practices. Longitudinal research may provide valuable insight into such endogeneity. Second, it is possible to include moderators to evaluate the way outcome variables, like employees' creative performance, change. Some of such variables that could operate as moderators are incentives for behavioural changes and task and resource support for job performance. Similarly, the relationship between individual values and expected behaviours or actions could be mediated by several variables such as attitudes and intentions. Future research could incorporate such moderating and mediating variables. Overall, we expect that the present study could stimulate more thinking and future research.

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Figures and Tables

Figure 1: Proposed conceptual model.

Figure 2: Statistical diagram with standardized path coefficients.
 Note: $*** p < .001$

Table 1. Organizational values – factor analysis

Item	Factor 1: Corporate sustenance	Factor 2: Management virtues	Factor 3: Ethical concerns
Breakthrough thinking	.899		
Creating value	.856		
Customer driven innovation focus	.845		
Tolerance for unpredictability	.845		
Focus on results	.774		
Continuous learning	.713		
Systems perspective		.840	
Prevention-based management		.813	
Continuous improvement of systems		.751	
Societal responsibility			.864
Environmental preservation			.790
Commitment to sustainability			.710
Eigenvalue*	4.397	2.837	2.403
Explained variation*	36.645	23.642	20.066
Cronbach's alpha	.830	.775	.827
AVE	.679	.643	.625
Construct reliability	.926	.843	.832

Note: * values for extracted components, i.e., rotation sum of squared loadings

Table 2. Individual values – factor analysis

Item	Factor 1: Moral	Factor 2: Competence
Loving (affectionate, tender)	.867	
Forgiving (willing to pardon others)	.862	
Helpful (working for the welfare of others)	.839	
Obedient (dutiful, respectful)	.797	
Honest (sincere, truthful)	.760	
Cheerful (lighthearted, joyful)	.754	
Polite (courteous, well- mannered)	.732	
Responsible (dependable, reliable)	.710	
Broadminded (open-minded)	.708	
Self-controlled (restrained, self- disciplined)		.880
Capable (competent, effective)		.829
Clean (neat, tidy)		.805
Ambitious (hard-working, aspiring)		.783
Courageous (standing up for your beliefs)		.766
Logical (consistent, rational)		.764
Imaginative (daring, creative)		.718
Independent (self-reliant, self-sufficient)		.713
Intellectual (intelligent, reflective)		.707
Eigenvalue*	2.543	2.406
Explained variation*	42.376	40.100
Cronbach's alpha	.849	.801
AVE	.613	.602
Construct reliability	.934	.931

Note: * values for extracted components, i.e., rotation sum of squared loadings

Table 3. Creative performance – factor analysis

Item	Creative performance
The work I produce is creative	.914
The work I produce is original	.903
The work I produce is adaptive	.869
Eigenvalue	3.476
Explained variation	57.929
Cronbach's alpha	.853
AVE	.802
Construct reliability	.924

Table 4. Correlations

Variable	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 Age	30	1.69								
2 Gender [◊]	-	-	.096							
3 Industry experience	4.98	1.67	.688**	.142						
4 Firm age [±]	2.39	.33	.119	.018	.066					
5 Firm size [±]	5.66	1.18	.069	.041	.005	.754**				
6 Strategic orientation [◊]	-	-	.046	.014	.033	.513**	.536**			
7 Organizational values	4.10	.42	.281**	.415**	.325**	.425**	.411**	.607**		
8 Individual values	4.31	.41	.409**	.512**	.430**	.145	.121	.318**	.534**	
9 Creativity	4.73	.44	.537**	.282**	.420**	.160	.138	.318**	.577**	.669**

Note: [◊] in nominal scale; [±] in log ln; ** $p < .01$

Table 5. Direct relationships of interest – summarized results

Direct relationship	β	R ² (Adj.)	F	Significance
H1 Strategic orientation -> Organizational values	.415	.369	46.24	P<.001
H2 Organizational values -> Individual values	.834	.794	207.93	P<.001
H3 Individual values -> Creative performance	.379	.332	34.91	P<.001
H4 Firm size -> Strategic orientation	.648	.423	64.17	P<.001
H5 Firm age -> Strategic orientation	.413	.294	42.16	P<.001
Strategic orientation -> Creative performance	.282	.176	19.23	P<.001
Organizational values -> Creative performance	.177	.127	11.19	P<.01
Firm size -> Creative performance	.040	.023	.36	Not significant
Firm age -> Creative performance	.061	.046	.82	Not significant

Table 6. Model comparison - Fit indices

Model	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1 Strategic orientation -> Organizational values-> Creative performance	11.50	.715	.146	.217
2 Strategic orientation -> Individual values-> Creative performance	4.021	.960	.880	.195
3 Strategic orientation -> Organizational values-> Individual values-> Creative performance	3.019	.963	.826	.091
4 Firm size -> Strategic orientation -> Organizational values-> Individual values-> Creative performance	2.330	.926	.877	.077
5 Firm age -> Strategic orientation -> Organizational values-> Individual values-> Creative performance	5.143	.775	.625	.136
6 (H6) Firm age, Firm size -> Strategic orientation -> Organizational values-> Individual values-> Creative performance	1.635	.974	.957	.053